

Rieko Kodama, the First Lady of SEGA – Part Two

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

Are you all ready to continue reminiscing about the great Rieko Kodama? If you recall, in our previous entry we left her at her early years at Sega. What came next? Well, Ms Kodama did not only work on character designs, visual assets, brochures, or cover art —her path as a creative was only just beginning. She would go on to craft entire, complex worlds. But... how did she manage to achieve this?

The Rise of Japanese Role-playing Games

It was the competition to enter the then-emerging market of Japanese RPGs —JRPGs— that led Sega to put Kodama at the helm of projects requiring not only her artistic talent but her creativity in a much broader sense.

This was no simple task, as by the mid-1980s there were already fully accomplished titles and established franchises both in the West and in Japan, such as *Wizardry*, which saw its first release, *Wizardry: Proving Grounds of the Mad Overlord*, in 1981 by Sir-Tech Software; *Ultima I: The First Age of Darkness* (1980) by Richard Garriott for Origin Systems; the first *Final Fantasy* (1987) by Hironobu Sakaguchi for Squaresoft; the first *Dragon Quest* by Yūji Horii for Enix; or the iconic *The Legend of Zelda* by Shigeru Miyamoto and Takashi Tezuka for Nintendo (1986).

The Japanese have demonstrated a true passion not only for their own culture —both traditional and popular, including anime and manga— but also for Western culture. Adding to this, role-playing video games found a genuine niche of players in the Land of the Rising Sun, just as tabletop role-playing games such as the original *Dungeons & Dragons* by Gygax and Arneson (1974) had. Over the years, they developed their own unique RPG style, combining their particular vision of European medieval culture with Japanese aesthetics and a variety of Japanese myths and creatures.

Kodama had already collaborated with the team on a project of this nature, *The Black Onyx* (1984), a video game originally released for the NEC PC-8801 and later ported to multiple platforms, which included members such as the Dutch/American Henk Rogers and Japanese developers like Eiji Kure and Rieko Kodama herself.

Sega made it clear, both after learning about these projects and seeing the participation of its employees in them and others: there was a slice of the market to claim, and they were not going to let it slip away. What did they come up with? To create their own Japanese RPG franchise, with Kodama herself at the helm. Unlike other companies at the time, Sega did not opt to release an RPG developed by a third party on their systems; instead, they did so with an in-house team.

The Innovation of *Phantasy Star* for Role-playing Games

This is how *Phantasy Star* was born in 1987, with a development team led by Rieko Kodama —artistic design and production— and Yūji Naka —programming—. For this future RPG project, Kodama was recruited, along with many other women —something uncommon in the industry at the time— both by Naka and the designer Kotarō Hayashida. Kodama and Naka would go on to work closely together on future projects.

Original cover of the first *Phantasy Star* (1987) for the Sega Mark III, featuring work by Rieko Kodama.

Being one of the first Mark III cartridges to include RAM for saving game progress, this title combined both two- and three-dimensional elements. The game world, characters, and city graphics were depicted using a mix of top-down and $\frac{3}{4}$ overhead perspectives—a technique known in English as a “top-down view”—, while the dungeons were shown in three dimensions, offering multiple levels to explore, traps, and numerous enemies in random encounters, as well as unique encounters.

This was truly revolutionary, as it introduced both three-dimensional graphics to consoles and the fact that the environments were not represented using wireframes—vectors or lines—as in other games of the same style, such as *Akalabeth: World of Doom* (1980) or *Ultima I* (1980)—both created by Richard Garriott—, but rather with detailed textures and animated enemies.

On the left, how the game world appears in *Phantasy Star*. In the centre, an image of a dungeon combat section against an enemy; and on the right, one of the game’s story sequences, narrated with images and text in the style of a visual novel.

But the revolution did not stop there, as *Phantasy Star* managed to blend science fiction with fantasy, incorporating magic and mythology into the game. The team seemed intent on creating a video game that paid homage to space operas such as George Lucas’s *Star Wars* (1977), to franchises like Frank Herbert’s *Dune* (first novel published in 1965), and to animated series such as *Ulysses 31* (1981). Players visit three planets in the fictional Algol system—also known as Algo—: Palma, which depicts an advanced civilisation; Motavia, a desert planet—a clear nod to *Dune*’s Arrakis—; and Dezorin, an icy planet inhabited by mystical races.

Characters can wield ranged sci-fi weapons, but also swords and other melee arms in a medieval style—even a lightsaber, in true *Star Wars* fashion. The heroes face a multitude of beasts that could have come straight from a medieval fantasy RPG, exploring dungeons among other locations. Magic is also part of this world, while the villain, Dark Falz—a recurring character throughout the series—combines elements of both fantasy and science fiction.

The franchise left such an impact that other major companies borrowed these ideas, and this blending of sci-fi and fantasy can be seen in *Final Fantasy*, especially *VI* (1994) and later *VII* (1997), as well as in *Chrono Trigger* and *Tales of Phantasia* (both from 1995). *Phantasy Star* was also among the first JRPGs to reach the West with a notably accurate translation, compared to the common standards at the time. Additionally, it offered something rare for RPGs—and even rarer for console games—: detailed character portraits showing reactions and expressions, which brought players closer to their emotions.

The Significance of Alis Landale

Phantasy Star was the first game to present players with a coherent mix of fantasy and science fiction. But that was not its only noteworthy feature, as it introduced one of the first female protagonists in an RPG —excluding characters created and customised by players in other games— Alis Landale, who is not simply a girl to be rescued, but the leader of her team.

The circumstances surrounding her, such as the death of her brother, strengthen her, and she ends up becoming a quasi-legendary figure within the *Phantasy Star* universe. Moments before his death in the prologue, her brother Nero begs her to expose the evil plans of King Lassic. Alis undergoes character development right from the opening moments of the game, evolving from merely seeking revenge for her brother's murder to fighting to save the entire Algol system.

Rieko Kodama's aim with this video game was to offer something different for the RPG audience, beyond what established titles like *Dragon Quest* were already presenting.

Up to that point, video games were typically targeted at a predominantly male audience—including *Dragon Quest* itself— as they were the primary players at the time. As noted in the previous article, Princess Kurumi went from being the protagonist of *Ninja Princess* to being a damsel to be rescued by a male character in adaptations. Kodama, however, envisioned characters appealing to players of both sexes, providing a female protagonist who could serve as a role model for female gamers, thereby encouraging more girls to take an interest in RPGs and video games in general.

Nonetheless, Rieko avoided the pitfall that some later franchises fell into, creating female characters who are irritating, invincible, all-knowing, or flawless. Alis was not invincible, excessively cold, nor unapproachable. We saw her display strength, but also suffer —since the very prologue. She was a human, relatable, believable character who made mistakes. This combination is what made her so beloved by players.

The Influence of Rieko Kodama and *Phantasy Star* on Other Franchises

Alis influenced other series, starting with Sega's own franchises. In *Shining Force* (1992), the party includes Mae, a centaur knight seeking revenge for the loss of her father —one of the first knights to join the team— as well as witches Tao, Anri, and Alef, who can defeat enemies with a single spell, and the adventurous princess Khris, who not only fights but also uses supportive magic.

Alis with her brother Nero during his final moments in *Phantasy Star: Arisa no Bōken*; the first of three choose-your-own-adventure-style books based on *Phantasy Star*. This first volume was published in 1989 by Futabasha, developed by Studio Hard Co. and Mitsutaka Ode, with illustrations by Kunio Aoki.

Likewise, *Tales of Phantasia* (1995, Wolfteam/Namco) featured a male protagonist, Cless Alvein, but also memorable female co-protagonists such as Mint Adnade, the honourable and noble priestess; the irreverent, charismatic, and independent witch Arche Klein; and the ninja Suzu Fujibayashi —the latter joining the party only in versions released after the original Super Nintendo edition.

We must also remember the Mana series, which in its second entry presented female characters like Primm, and in *Seiken Densetsu 3 (Trials of Mana)* gave major playable characters such as the mage Angela, the cleric Charlotte, and the Amazon princess Riesz.

The influence of *Phantasy Star* extended beyond female representation, as the game explored deeper themes than merely saving the world —though this is also part of the narrative. It tackled mature and dark topics such as revenge, violence, and population control, alongside positive concepts like justice and sacrifice. Moreover, Kodama’s visual style, reminiscent of anime and manga of the era, inspired other RPGs to embrace Japanese cultural aesthetics much more prominently. Previously, many Japanese games had aimed to emulate Western visuals, with *Dragon Quest* —designed by mangaka Akira Toriyama— being a notable exception.

Alis —in the centre— fights alongside her companions in *Phantasy Star*: the cat Myau —part of a fictional race known in English as a “musk cat”— (left, front), her ally, the fighter Tyron/Odin (left, back), and the thaumaturge Lutz/Noah (right).

Phantasy Star was Sega's proof that it could successfully develop its own RPG franchise, as well as the consolidation of Rieko Kodama as a creative force in the world of video games. It became a celebrated franchise, offering players a multitude of titles set in its universe, but what else emerged from Kodama's mind thereafter? We will detail it in the future! Stay tuned!

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** Eurogamer, Phantasy Star Fandom, Sega Retro, Szczepaniak, J. (2014), *The Untold History of Japanese Game Developers: Volume 1*. SMG Szczepaniak | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
- **Images sourced from:** SMS Power, Sega Bits, IGN, Sega Retro

Licence and original publication

- **Licence:** This article and its content are published under **CC BY 4.0**, allowing sharing and adaptation of the material provided the source and author are cited
- *Originally published on CoolJapan.es on 4 November 2025 —Rieko Kodama, la gran dama de SEGA – Segunda parte—*
- *This version is a faithful translation into English by Andrés Domenech Alcaide*